

Understanding pay satisfaction in public sector: Evidence from Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Purpose: The research investigated the determinants of pay satisfaction of executive-level employees in public sector of Sri Lanka, which follows an open pay system.

Design/methodology/approach: The perceptions of equity, love of money, justice, and seven individual and socio-demographic characteristics were investigated as determinants of pay satisfaction. The survey methodology is used for data collection.

Findings: The findings showed equity, love of money, justice, the years of work experience in public sector, the number of income earners in the family and the number of dependents in the family as the significant predictors of pay satisfaction. Gender is identified as a significant predictor of love of money.

Originality/value: The study investigated the dynamics of pay satisfaction in a novel research context - i.e., public sector, an open pay system, gender equality in the pay system and an Asian developing country.

Key words: Equity, gender, justice, love of money, pay satisfaction, public sector

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Pay can be considered as the rationale for employees to enter and remain in the labour market across countries. Pay comprises the most important component of the reward system of public sector in any country. Understanding pay practices and employees' satisfaction with pay are of great importance to public sector as an employer as well as to its employees. From the point of view of public sector, pay constitute a significant portion of any government's operating expenses, and governments naturally question the impact of pay practices on broader scale. Public sector is increasingly concerned about prevailing pay practices and avenues to reduce labour costs while ensuring that employees elicit productive behaviour at work (Feng et al., 2020; Murphy et al., 2020). Futuristic governments can use its pay practices as a competitive strategy to attract competent individuals to the public sector (Murphy et al., 2020). Due to such competing interests of governments, the world has witnessed that public sector pay practices becoming increasingly formalized and sophisticated.

From the employees point of view, pay communicates a wealth of information about an organization's priorities, achievements and contribution to work and workplace, security, social standing as well as success in life. Among many uses of pay in the lives of individuals, they use it as the "frame of reference" to evaluate their satisfaction and to compare with others (McClelland, 1967, p. 10; Tang, 1992). Hence, satisfaction with pay is an attitude developed by employees after an assessment of one's pay with compared to the pay of referent others. Academic and practitioner communities have a relatively clear understanding of the numerous desirable and undesirable consequences of employees' attitudes towards pay due to the sheer volume of publications on the consequences of pay satisfaction. However, it is less clear about employees' pay satisfaction and the determinants of pay satisfaction, especially in public sector with open pay systems.

In the above context, the two main objectives of the research were to investigate 1) whether pay satisfaction is determined by the perceptions of equity, love of money and justice; and 2) whether pay satisfaction is determined by individual and socio-demographic characteristics, namely gender, age, the highest level of education, marital status, the years of work experience in public sector, the number of income earners in the family and the number of dependents in the family. In addition, as a by-product of the analysis, data were also generated

for the effect of gender on the perceptions of individuals' love of money, equity and justice prevailing in public sector.

The present study intends to make important original contributions to the theory and practices, and the findings will be of interest to academics, researchers, practitioners and policy makers alike in both developed and developing worlds. First, a limited number of studies empirically investigated pay satisfaction involving all four dimensions, i.e., pay level, pay raise, benefits and structure/administration (see Williams et al., 2006). Many studies considered pay satisfaction as a single-item construct (one-item scale to evaluate pay satisfaction, for example Parker and Brummel, 2016), or considered as a unidimensional construct (e.g., an average was created using a multi-item scale, for example Treuren and Frankish, 2014) or confined to one selected aspect of pay satisfaction of Heneman and Schwab's (1985) multi-dimensions (for example, pay level to the exclusion of other three dimensions, see meta-analysis by Williams et al., 2006). One of the reasons for this failure to identify pay satisfaction as a multidimensional construct may be due to the difficulties of obtaining primary data on the entire spectrum of pay. The present study addressed this shortfall by adopting Heneman and Schwab's (1985) conceptualization of pay satisfaction, which takes into consideration four distinct facets of pay satisfaction, namely level, raises, benefits and structure/administration.

Second, on the one hand, employees' pay satisfaction could be determined by constructs that are related to pay practices itself or aspects that could be manipulated by an organization's pay administrators. On the other hand, employees' pay satisfaction could be determined by constructs that are unrelated to an organization's pay system. Williams et al. (2006) state that the literature on employees' attitudes to pay has evolved independently- with limited attention to both sides of arguments. Therefore, the present study covered both spectrums, and investigated effects of equity, love of money, justice, individual characteristics (such as gender and age) and socio-demographic characteristics (such as number of income earners and dependents in the family).

Third, in connection to the above, the theories such as equity and justice (Adams 1963; Bies and Moag 1986) for example, argue that employees evaluate actual pay with multiple personal standards in determining their satisfaction with pay. Therefore, the present study analysed the effects of three dimensions of justice (distributive, procedural and interactional) against

four dimensions of pay satisfaction to understand the relative importance in the prediction of pay satisfaction. It should be noted that interactional justice received the least empirical attention to date as a predictor of pay satisfaction. Hence, the present study attempts to fill these gaps in the literature.

Fourth, we investigated the dynamics of pay satisfaction in a novel research context - i.e., public sector, an open pay system, gender equality in the pay system and an Asian developing country. Sri Lanka is one of the very few developing countries that has achieved a high level of human development in consistent with high-income countries (Arun et al., 2013). The Sri Lankan public sector adopted an open pay system. The literature on public sector and/or an open pay system so far has not provided definitive or generalizable insights backed by empirical studies on how equity, love of money, justice and individual and socio-demographic characteristics determine pay satisfaction. For example, in the context of pay-level transparency Hartmann and Slapničar (2012) report that distributive justice operates as a better predictor of employees' attitudes than procedural justice. In public sector with an open pay system, Day (2011) reports that interactional justice is not significant in the prediction of pay satisfaction. Tang et al. (2005) reports that love of money attitudes of employees is different in public sector when pay-level transparency exists. This suggests that the determinants of pay satisfaction may be highly dependent on the context under investigation.

Literature review

Pay satisfaction

Pay satisfaction is an attitude developed by employees after evaluating one's pay with compared to different pay-related dimensions of importance. The majority of literature on pay satisfaction is in agreement with Heneman and Schwab's (1985) identification of it as a multidimensional construct (see Williams et al., 2006) consisted of pay level, benefits, raise and structure/administration. This multidimensional pay satisfaction construct has been tested and validated ever since in different contexts. The literature also emphasises that when Heneman and Schwab's (1985) all the dimensions of pay are not included in the measurement of pay satisfaction, the resulting outcomes of such research should be interpreted cautiously (Jawahar and Stone, 2011; Day 2011; Tran, 2016).

Of the four distinct facets of pay satisfaction, pay level is the current direct pay an employee receives in terms of wages/salary. An employee's satisfaction with pay level is identified as "a result of an employee comparing his/her actual pay level with the pay level he/she thinks entitled to" (Schreurs et al., 2015, p. 1523). Pay level is identified to provide both instrumental and symbolic value to an employee. From the instrumental perspective, pay level signifies "money is the best gift of all because the recipient can use it to buy exactly what he or she wants" (Lea and Webley, 2006, p. 171). From the symbolic perspective, it signifies a feeling of competence, i.e., an employee's capacity to perform or career success (Hakonen et al., 2011). Employees who are satisfied with their pay levels generally feel more competent and respected than those who were less satisfied with their pay levels (Schreurs et al., 2015). Some recent studies confined to investigate only the pay level dimension of pay satisfaction (e.g., Schreurs et al., 2015, Chen et al., 2015).

The raise dimension of pay satisfaction takes into consideration the change in pay level in terms of increments/increases, and also the process involved in making the decision of raise and the supervisor's role in the outcome. Heneman and Schwab (1985) suggest that an employee, who received typically higher raises in the past years should be more satisfied with his/her raises compared to those who did not receive such. Benefits dimension of pay satisfaction consists of indirect pay that an employee receives in variety of forms, such as medical, retirement, payments for time not worked and many other non-financial receipts. Structure and administration dimension of pay satisfaction consists of the relative worth of different jobs, internal pay hierarchy, pay policies, procedures surrounding the administration of the pay system, and the perceived adequacy of pay-system administration. When information related to pay structure and administration are communicated and understood by employees, such employees would report a higher satisfaction with structure and administration of pay. Heneman and Schwab (1985) and many others empirically tested and supported (such as Jawahar and Stone, 2011; Day 2011) that each of the dimension represent distinct albeit related evaluations of pay satisfaction. For example, an employee might be satisfied with his/her pay level but not with structure and administration of pay. Figure 1 shows the simplified conceptual model developed for the study.

Figure 1

Equity

Equity theory (Adams, 1963) states that employees evaluate their rewards by comparing the ratio of outcomes they receive (e.g. pay) to their inputs (e.g. work effort). If the comparison leads to perceive that outcome-to-input ratio corresponds, employees believe that resources are fairly distributed (Schreurs et al., 2015). For this comparison, employees do not necessarily rely on absolute values but on relative values, and they may use multiple personal standards through a process of individual and social comparison. Hence, the Rice et al. (1990) identify four distinctive forms of pay equity that is relevant for pay satisfaction, namely:

- pay employees feel they deserve or should receive (what one thinks he/she deserves),
- the perceived minimum acceptable pay for which an employee would perform his/her work (what one needs),
- pay others within the organization receive (what internal others have), and
- pay others outside the organization doing comparable jobs in the relevant labour market receive (what one expects to have).

Each of these four forms are reviewed, in brief, below.

With regard to pay employees feel that they deserve, individual-level equity is referred as the basis of the relative contribution with compared to those who are working on the same job in a particular organization. Performance appraisal is typically used to achieve individual-level equity.

The perceived minimum acceptable pay implies instrumental uses such as to purchase desired goods and services and maintain status and self-validation. In short, this is about one's perception of his/her personal finances, debt, savings and investment (Kim and Garman, 2004).

The pay others within the organization receive is the pay differentials maintained at different levels of vertical hierarchy of the organization. Since jobs differ in terms of compensable factors such as effort, skill, education, working conditions and responsibility, pay should be fairly distributed within an organization (Tang and Tang, 2012). Job evaluation is used to achieve internal pay equity.

Finally, salary surveys are used to achieve external equity in terms of pay others outside the organization doing comparable jobs in the relevant labour market receive. Maintaining external equity is important for competitiveness in the labour market (Tang and Tang, 2012).

According to equity theory, an employee's level of pay satisfaction is determined by comparing actual pay with above four pay equity standards. Torre et al. (2015) showed that perceived internal and external equity are associated with perceived pay satisfaction; Kim and Garman (2004) showed that the minimum acceptable pay for which employees would perform their work explains a significant portion of pay satisfaction. Based on the above reviewed literature, it is hypothesised:

H1: Equity significantly positively predicts pay satisfaction.

Love of money

Money is a measure of value, and it continues to be the foremost means of recognising and modifying human behaviour at work. Love of money operates as an individual's "frame of reference", "standard" or "aspiration" when making judgements on pay, which can be used to evaluate pay satisfaction (Tang 1992). Love of money is identified to be comprised of several affective (such as rich, good and evil), behavioural (such as motivator and budget) and cognitive (success, respect, power, and important) dimensions (for a detailed review, refer to Tang 1992; Tang and Tang, 2012), and the meaning of money is "in the eye of the beholder" (McClelland, 1967, p. 10). For example, an individual may treat money as a symbol of success (Furnham, 2014) and for them, money represents achievement, security and autonomy on a score card (Tang, 1992). Tang (2016, 2020) and Tang et al. (2018) further suggest that individuals monitor their own affective, behavioural and cognitive dimensions of love of money, and use these dimensions to evaluate options and select strategies to accomplish financial goals, which lead to

reach ultimate success and subjective well-being. Individuals with higher levels of love of money always want to have more money. In the context of work, employees work for their pay and they want to have more pay, i.e., when an employee bestows a high love of money, he/she may pay more attention to it and expect to receive a large pay (for a detailed review see Tang 1992; Tang and Tang, 2012). Previous research established a negative relationship between love of money and pay satisfaction (Tang et al., 2005). Overall, employees with higher levels of love of money may have low levels of pay satisfaction. Therefore, it hypothesised:

H2: Love of money significantly negatively predicts pay satisfaction.

Justice

Justice represents one of the major mechanisms through which employees judge their pay, and in turn their satisfaction with pay. Employees compare their pay with multiple justice standards, such as distributive justice, procedural justice and interactional justice to derive pay satisfaction (Adams 1963; Bies and Moag 1986). Distributive justice evaluates whether an employee's pay is equitably allocated, which is connected to his/her performance level (Adams, 1963). Procedural justice evaluates the perceived fairness of the decision-making processes and procedures that are used to decide and distribute the outcome allocation (pay) (Adams, 1963). Interactional justice evaluates the social side of justice, which comprised of informational justice and interpersonal justice (Bies and Moag 1986). Informational justice refers to the perceived degree of fairness in providing explanations on pay allocation decisions- thoroughly, clearly, truthfully, adequately and timely (Jawahar and Stone, 2011; Day, 2011). Interpersonal justice refers to the perceived degree of fairness when supervisors/managers treat his/her subordinates with courtesy, dignity and respect (Day, 2011; Jawahar and Stone, 2011). The literature specifies relationships between these justice dimensions and pay satisfaction building on two-factor model (Sweeney and McFarlin 1993) and agent-system model (Bies and Moag 1986). The relationship between each of these justice perceptions and pay satisfaction is reviewed in brief below.

Distributive justice. The two-factor model of justice (Sweeney and McFarlin 1993) proposes that employees' perception of distributive justice is more closely related to the evaluation of person-referenced outcomes or individual contributions, i.e., on the "ends". For

example, the pay level of a job, is based on the pay grade and job analysis information on the requirements of skills, abilities and experiences; pay raise is based on individual performance appraisal. Accordingly, distributive justice results from the evaluation of an employees' pay level or pay raises, for example, through social comparisons with referent others (Adams, 1963). However, the success of this comparison depends on an employee's knowledge of what other employees receive (Williams et al., 2006). Building on the literature that showed satisfaction with pay level and pay raise are more strongly predicted by the perception of distributive justice (see Sweeney and McFarlin 1993; Williams et al., 2006), it is hypothesised:

H3a: Distributive justice significantly positively predicts pay satisfaction, and the prediction will be stronger for pay level and raise satisfaction.

Procedural justice. According to the two-factor model of justice (Sweeney and McFarlin 1993), the employees' perception of procedural justice is more closely related to the evaluation of system-referenced or organisation outcomes/organizational systems, i.e., on the "means". Accordingly, procedural justice results from process and decision control, the consistent application of bias-free procedures that are based on trustworthy accurate information sources adhering to moral standards of organisations' members as well as availability and the use of means to rectify bad decisions. Employees' participation in pay system design and organizational practices in relation to communicating individual performance-related information, grievance handling and employee voice help to ensure procedural justice perceptions (Moorman, 1991; Day, 2011). Pay structure/administration policies and benefits operate at the organizational level instead of based on employees' characteristics such as skills, knowledge and experience or their contribution. Therefore, employees' satisfaction with benefits and pay structure/administration are more strongly predicted by the perception of procedural justice (see Sweeney and McFarlin 1993; Williams et al., 2006). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H3b: Procedural justice significantly positively predicts pay satisfaction, and the prediction will be stronger for benefits and structure/administration satisfaction

Interactional justice. Both interpersonal and informational justice dimensions of interactional justice are associated with “agent-referenced outcomes”. These are outcomes usually over which “agents” or supervisors have power to control when compared to “system-referenced outcomes” discussed under procedural justice (Day, 2011). For example, the communication of information relating to pay level, raise, benefits and pay structure/administration could influence informational justice. Further, influence or control that supervisors/managers have over outcome allocation (pay) decisions, such as control/influence over decisions on raise, benefits, structured/administration influence interpersonal justice. However, so far few empirical research investigated the effect of interactional justice on pay satisfaction, and these studies do not provide conclusive evidence. For example, Day (2011) reports that interactional justice is essentially unrelated to pay satisfaction. Jawahar and Stone (2011) report that informational justice predict satisfaction with pay level and structure/administration but interpersonal justice did not predict satisfaction with pay raise. Since the effect of interactional justice on pay satisfaction is inconclusive, and based on the above reviewed previous studies, it is hypothesised:

H3c: Interactional justice significantly positively predicts pay satisfaction, and the prediction will be stronger for pay level, raise and structure/administration than benefits satisfaction

Individual and socio-demographic characteristics

Gender

Differences in perceptions towards money. The meaning and personal significance of money and possessions are found to differ sharply and consistently convey different meanings for women and men (Rudmin 1990). Money provides self-esteem and a sense of power as an inextricable part of overall male image and attractiveness, and males are more likely to view money from a functional/self-oriented perspective. In contrast, money provides a means of hedonistic and expressive pursuits for women, and they are more likely to view money from a symbolic/other-oriented perspective (Rudmin, 1990). Money is not only a prestige symbol for women but a passport to personal security and tranquillity, a means of immediate acquisition of treasured

possessions and self-extensions, a facility for enhancing relationships as well as a means of living a satisfying and comfortable lifestyle (Prince, 1993). Further, although males are more likely to be obsessed with money (Furnham, 2014), “women more likely to exhibit a stronger sense of money hunger; more likely than men to express a sense of frustration about not having enough money; more likely than men to be envious of those who have more money than they have” (Prince, 1993, p. 179). However, when taking the advantage of earnings as a symbol of power, prestige and success, men shows more direct and undisguised source of power where as women shows less ability or restraint to use monetary power (Atkinson and Boles, 1984; Prince, 1993).

Differences in the treatment of personal income in households. The literature suggests explanations for the differential treatment of women’s and men’s personal income. Two of such explanations more relevant to the present study are on women’s/wives’ participation in the labour market (Zuo, 1997) and wives’ financial contribution in households (Deutsch et al., 2003). With regard to women’s participation in the labour market, the situation of gender-pay gap is important. The literature suggests that men and women were continue to be subjected to a longstanding differential pay treatment in the labour market, where female employees are paid lower than their male counterparts (Sidani, 2013). However, at the end of 20th century, the percentage of women earning more than their husbands are found to be on the rise (Zuo, 1997). Further, fewer men felt uncomfortable of wives earning more money than them (Willinger, 1993), and both men and women felt more gratitude and appreciation towards the highest income earner in the family (Deutsch et al., 2003). With regard to wives’ financial contribution in households, at the end of 20th century, women’s earnings are not considered peripheral; more men reported considering wives as co-providers of income of the family (Zuo, 1997). When women assume more contribution for the family income, they exercise more influence over family decisions; involve in comparatively lower percentage of domestic labour; consider their careers as relatively more important. Further, men maintain more support for the career advancement of their wives (Willinger, 1993) and men felt pride in their wives’ career success (Atkinson and Boles, 1984).

Differences in pay expectations. The literature suggests explanations for women's lower pay expectations than men. Three of such explanations more relevant to the present study were on men's and women's differences in career path choices (Jamali et al., 2008; Major and Konar, 1984), the level of education and training (Travis et al., 2009), and pay referents used (Loscocco and Spitze, 1991). With regard to career path choices, women's career choices are identified as unique, and segregated to certain occupations; they are often underrepresented in jobs related to science and engineering (Major and Konar, 1984). As a result, the jobs women occupy are often lower paid (Major and Konar, 1984); hours worked (job inputs) may be shorter than men (Major and Konar, 1984); experience career interruptions than men (Jamali et al., 2008), and careers are of shorter duration than men (Jamali et al., 2008). With regard to differences in the level of education and training, often women are rated lower due to the lack of opportunities for personal investment in pertinent education, training and continuous development stems from family responsibilities (Travis et al., 2009). With regard to pay referents, women's pay referents are identified as other women, who are either unemployed or working in similar but lower paying jobs (Loscocco and Spitze, 1991, P. 2). Overall, due to such reasons, it is suggested that women have lower pay expectations and perceive lower levels of pay to be fair.

Differences in pay satisfaction. In the investigation of pay satisfaction, some studies treated gender as a control variable while few other studies investigated its effect on pay satisfaction. The studies that treated gender as a control variable reported that gender does not have significant correlation ($p < .05$) with the satisfaction of pay level, benefits, raise or structure/administration, and as a result did not analyse its effects beyond simple correlation (e.g., Tang et al., 2012). With regard studies that investigated the effect of gender on pay satisfaction, some studies found that in spite of gender-pay gap, women express levels of job and pay satisfaction similar to or even higher than those of men (Loscocco and Spitze, 1991). However, the gender effect on pay satisfaction is not conclusive. For example, Keaveny and Inderrieden (2000) found women are more satisfied than men with pay level; Bhave and Kramer (2013) did not find gender effect on pay satisfaction. Based on all the previous studies reviewed above on gender, it is hypothesised:

H4: Females are significantly more satisfied with pay than males

Education

The rationale for education to be a predictor of pay satisfaction is that education is an investment, and employees expect pay (return) commensurate with the investment in education (Bhave and Kramer, 2013). The literature theorizes and provides support for education as one of the main characteristics for earnings inequality (see Arun et al., 2013 for review). Schreurs et al. (2015) state that pay level conveys a feeling about competence, where competence is defined as related to knowledge, skills and experience. This supports the argument that the level of education could be a predictor of pay satisfaction. However, Prince (1993) nor Schreurs et al. (2015) investigated the effect of education/competence on pay satisfaction. When considering the relationship between the level of education and pay satisfaction, Bhave and Kramer (2013) found that employees who had a higher level of education attainment judge their pay differently than employees who had lower level of education attainment. Loscocco and Spitze (1991, p. 12) evaluated the effect of education on pay satisfaction and stated “the pay satisfaction of both men and women is negatively (and marginally) influenced by education”. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H5: The level of education significantly negatively predicts pay satisfaction

Age

The literature identifies age as a main characteristic that influences earnings inequality (for review see Arun et al., 2013). Some studies investigated age-related differences in pay preferences of employees (e.g., Stringer et al., 2011). For example, Von Bonsdorff (2011) found older employees’ preference for pay level and raises whereas Stringer et al. (2011) found that employees do not judge their pay differently by age. When considering the effect of age in the prediction of pay satisfaction, Loscocco and Spitze (1991) found a positive relationship between age and pay satisfaction, where older employees are more satisfied with their pay. Based on these empirical evidence, it is hypothesized:

H6: Age significantly positively predicts pay satisfaction

Years of work experience

The rationale for work experience is based on the assumption that employees may expect return (pay) commensurate with their investments in years of dedicated service (Bhave and Kramer, 2013). Organizations consider seniority as a potentially legitimate basis for pay decisions; the pay level of an employee depends on the years of work experience with the organization (Schreurs et al., 2015). Arun et al. (2013) when estimating an earnings function for Sri Lanka found a significant positive effect of years of work experience on earnings. Few studies (such as Bhave and Kramer, 2013; Kim and Garman, 2004) investigated the effects of work experience on pay satisfaction although findings are not conclusive, where some studies identify (e.g., Kim and Garman, 2004) and some not identifying (e.g., Bhave and Kramer (2013) work experience as a significant predictor of pay satisfaction. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H7: Number of years of work experience in public sector significantly positively predicts pay satisfaction

Marital status, number of income earners and number of dependents

Few studies such as Bhave and Kramer (2013), Keaveny and Inderrieden (2000) and Loscocco and Spitze (1991) investigated pay satisfaction in the light of marital status, dependents and income earners in the family. According to Loscocco and Spitze (1991) married and dual earner families perceived another source of income in the family, which unmarried employees did not have. In this regard, Keaveny and Inderrieden (2000 p. 376) state “one’s assessment of the family financial situation appears to be related to pay satisfaction”. These suggest that not only marital status but also the number of income earners in the family is also important in pay satisfaction. With regard to the number of dependents in the family, Loscocco and Spitze (1991 p. 7) found that when there is a presence of dependent children, both men and women employees are more likely to perceive that a given level of income is inadequate. Bhave and Kramer (2013) also found that when employees have a greater number of dependents, they tend to perceive that the pay received is not adequate with compared to employees, who have fewer dependents. Although there were very limited number of previous studies, based on these, it is hypothesised:

H8: Marital status significantly predicts pay satisfaction, where married employees are more satisfied than otherwise

H9: The number of income earners in the family significantly positively predicts pay satisfaction

H10: The number of dependents in the family significantly negatively predicts pay satisfaction

Methodology

Sample

Employees in the public sector in Sri Lanka operate in a highly regularized environment created by the Public Services Commission (PSC) of Sri Lanka. Its Establishment Code provides a single source of reference specifying uniform set of practices for all employees in the public sector. Hence, pay, like all other public sector employment-related practices, is governed by the Establishment Code of the PSC and does not change by the geographic region of the job holder. The sample of the study was restricted to individuals employed in executive job positions in public sector organizations in Colombo district, which is considered as the main commercial and financial hub of the country, and also living expenses suggested to be higher compared to other areas of the country. The individuals were identified through the directories of ministries, departments and statutory organizations. A contact person was identified from each public sector organization, and participants for the survey were identified using convenience and snowball sampling methods. Together with the author of this paper, each contact person selected volunteers to participate in the study. In this process, every attempt was made to select a cross section of respondents representing diverse individual and socio-demographic characteristics. A self-administered survey questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument. The survey instrument was in the English language, which is considered as a national language of the country. Prior to the distribution of the questionnaire, all the measures used for the study were pre-tested with a sample of 30 public sector employees. Each voluntary participant was briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution. Participants' responses were

anonymous. Of the 500 questionnaires distributed, 346 fully completed responses received yielding a response rate of 69%.

With regard to the characteristics of the sample, 41.4% were from the age group of 25 to 40 years while 58.6% were from the age group of 41 to 55 years. Females were 49.6% and males were 50.4%. It is a must for employees in executive job positions in public sector to possess at least Bachelor's degree. Of the respondents, 34.6% had Bachelor's degree as the highest level of education while 65.4% reported having post-graduate degree as the highest level of education. The average years of work experience in the public sector was 13.5 (SD = 9.7). 83.6% identified as married while 16.4% identified as either never married, separated, divorced or widowed. The average number of income earners in the family was 2.1 (SD = 1.5), and the average number of dependents in the family was 2.03 (SD = 1.1). Appendix 1 summarises statistics for the year 2016 from the Department of Census and Statistics (2018) on the country-wide distribution of public sector employees for the comparison purpose with the sample characteristics of the present study.

Measures

All the item measures used are listed in Tables 1 to 4. *Pay satisfaction* was measured using the 18-item pay satisfaction scale of Heneman and Schwab (1985). *Pay equity* was measured using the 7-item scale, of which three items were adapted from Tang et al. (2005). These three items were on the perceptions of internal and external pay equity comparison. Four items were developed for the study to denote the perception of pay employees feel they deserve, minimum acceptable pay to purchase desired goods/services, and pay required to maintain status and self-validation (refer to Rice et al., 1990; Kim and Garman, 2004). All these items were on a five-point scale ranging from 1 (very dissatisfied) to 5 (very satisfied). Distributive justice was measured with the 5-item distributive justice scale of Price and Mueller (1986). Procedural justice was measured with the 5-items of Moorman (1991). Interactional justice was measured with the 6-items of Moorman (1991). *Love of money* was measured using Money Ethic Scale of Tang (1995). Tang (1995) identified three distinctive money attitudes as success (a cognitive component), budget (a behavioural component), and evil (an affective component). Of the 12-

item scale (Tang, 1995) a large part of the common variance of the love of money construct comes from the 8-item factor representing “success” (“money is a sign of one's success”). For the study, this 8-item scale of success-related money attitudes were used to fit the purpose of the study.

Individual and socio-demographic characteristics. Gender was coded as 0 (male) and 1 (female). The highest level of education was coded as 0 (Bachelor’s degree) and 1 (post graduate degree). The age was coded as 0 (25 to 40 years) and 1 (41 to 55 years). Marital status was coded as 0 (single to include never married, separated, divorced, or widowed) and 1 (married). Years of work experience in the public sector was collected in years (ratio scale). The number of income earners in the family and the number of dependents in the family were also collected in ratio scales.

Methods of data analysis

First, data were tested for common method variance using Harman’s single-factor test. Neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance (refer to Hair et al., 2006). Second, Principle component factor analysis with Varimax rotation was performed on variables to ensure (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias. In doing so, Convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE. when evaluating fit-measures, we adhered to the thresholds stipulated by Hair et al. (2006). Third, regression analysis was used to identify predictors of pay satisfaction. Fourth, independent sample t-test was used to determine whether there are significant differences by individual and socio-demographic characteristics as predicted in H4 to H10. Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) is used since it provides all the required tools for the above analysis.

Results

The results of factor analysis for equity, love of money, justice and pay satisfaction are shown in Tables from 1 to 4. Table 5 shows descriptive statistics and correlations between the variables.

Tables 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5

Regression analysis was used to answer the first and second research questions. All individual and socio-demographic variables were first entered into the model. The results showed that gender, the highest level of education, age and marital status did not significantly predict satisfaction with pay, i.e., pay level, pay raise, benefits or structure/administration. In this regard, Hair et al. (2006, p. 285) state that when the number of non-significant independent variables in the model increases, the adjusted R^2 decreases leading to the overall poorer fit of the model, and emphasise the need of removing non-significant variables for a better fit. Therefore, these four individual and socio-demographic characteristics were removed from the model and re-run the analysis following the process described above. The subsequent results are summarised in Table 6. The summary of all hypotheses testing is summarised in Table 7.

Table 6

With regard to the effect of equity (Table 6, step 2), both components of equity, i.e., adequacy and comparative, significantly positively predict all components of pay satisfaction, Therefore, H1 is supported. The results further show that the effects of both adequacy ($\beta = 0.602, p < 0.001$) and comparative ($\beta = 0.524, p < 0.001$) are the highest on satisfaction with pay level. Love of money (Table 6, step 2) significantly negatively predicts all components of pay satisfaction, supporting H2. Further, the effect of love of money is the highest on satisfaction with pay level ($\beta = -0.435, p < 0.001$). Distributive justice significantly positively predicts all components of pay satisfaction; its effect on satisfaction with pay level ($\beta = 0.501, p < 0.001$) is the highest followed by the effect on pay raise ($\beta = 0.490, p < 0.001$). This supports H3a. Procedural justice significantly positively predicts all components of pay satisfaction; its effect on satisfaction with pay structure/administration ($\beta = 0.402, p < 0.001$) is the highest

followed by the effect on benefits ($\beta = 0.378, p < 0.001$). This supports H3b. Interactional justice significantly positively predicts all components of pay satisfaction; its effect on satisfaction with benefits ($\beta = 0.214, p < 0.001$) is the lowest. This supports H3c.

With regard of the effect of individual and socio-demographic variables on pay satisfaction, the years of work experience in the public sector (Table 6, step 2) has positive significant effect on all dimensions of pay satisfaction. This suggests that employees with more years of work experience in the public sector were more satisfied with their pay, supporting H7. The effect of work experience is at the strongest for pay level ($\beta = 0.775, p < 0.001$). The number of income earners in the family (Table 6, step 2) has positive significant effects on pay level ($\beta = 0.108, p < 0.05$), pay raise ($\beta = 0.101, p < 0.05$) and benefits ($\beta = 0.110, p < 0.05$). Although the effect of income earners on pay structure/administration ($\beta = 0.048, p > 0.05$) is positive it is not statistically significant. Therefore, H9 is partially supported. The number of dependents in the family has negative significant effects on pay level ($\beta = -0.124, p < 0.05$), pay raise ($\beta = -0.113, p < 0.05$) and benefits ($\beta = -0.108, p < 0.05$). Although the effect of income earners on pay structure/administration ($\beta = 0.066, p > 0.05$) is negative it is not statistically significant. Therefore, H10 is partially supported.

With regard to each dimension of pay satisfaction (Table 6, step 2), the adjusted R^2 of 0.775 reveals that the final model explained 78% of the variance in the satisfaction with pay level ($p < 0.001$); the adjusted R^2 of 0.559 reveals that final model explained 56% of the variance in the satisfaction with pay raise ($p < 0.001$); the adjusted R^2 of 0.641 reveals that final model explained 64% of the variance in the satisfaction with benefits ($p < 0.001$); the adjusted R^2 of 0.621 reveal that final model explained 62% of the variance in the satisfaction with pay structure/administration ($p < 0.001$). Table 7 summarizes the results of all hypotheses tested.

Table 7

Although gender (H4), the highest level of education (H5), age (H6) and marital status (H8) did not significantly predict any of the dimensions of pay satisfaction, to understand the ways in which these four variables influence pay satisfaction, independent sample t-tests were

conducted. The mean values suggested that females are more satisfied with all the components of pay satisfaction (level, raise, benefits and structure/administration) than males; employees with postgraduate degrees are more satisfied with all the components of pay satisfaction than others; older employees are more satisfied with all the components of pay satisfaction than younger employees. The study also investigated whether there are significant gender differences in the perceptions of equity, love of money and justice. The results of t-test are shown in Table 8. The results suggest that gender differences are significant for love of money ($t = -2.692; p < 0.01$) where females have more love of money (mean = 4.60) than males (mean = 4.36).

Tables 8

Discussion of findings with implications for theory and practice

The research investigated pay satisfaction of executive level employees in public sector organizations in Sri Lanka. The present study is one of the few studies conducted on pay in the public sector and also one of the very few studies conducted in a developing country context. The results showed that equity, love of money and justice are important perceptions that significantly predict all the dimensions of pay satisfaction. The results further showed that the years of work experience in the public sector, the number of income earners in the family and the number of dependents in the family have significant effects on pay satisfaction. In addition, the results showed that love of money of females is significantly higher than males. Overall, the findings have implications for theory and practice, which are discussed below under three headings - implications for theory, implications for practice, and implications specific to the public sector and open pay systems.

Theoretical contributions of the findings

The context of the present study, i.e., public sector, has theoretical contributions. Although it is not the intention of the present study to make a distinction between open and closed pay systems, the present study was conducted in the context of an open pay system. The context

itself provided an interesting research setting and the findings have implications, and these can be discussed under several areas.

First, it is evident from the findings that the effect of distributive justice is stronger than procedural justice for all dimensions of pay satisfaction. The fairness heuristic theory of Van den Bos et al. (1997) states that when employees know each other's pay, and are able to judge their pay outcomes, the perception of distributive justice becomes more important; when employees are unaware of each other's pay, and unable to judge their pay outcomes, they will rely on policies and procedures to make judgements on the fairness of their pay. Although not similar to the present study context, Hartmann and Slapničar (2012) also provided closer observations. Although the importance of open pay systems is identified in the management literature, there are only a handful of empirical studies conducted on open pay systems, and also in public sector. Therefore, researchers and practitioners alike would be interested to learn more about pay satisfaction in such contexts. Present study, therefore, makes an important contribution to the literature on public sector, specifically the pay systems of executive-level employees in public sector.

Second, Colella et al. (2007) suggest that pay distribution (pay level and pay raises) could be narrower in open pay systems with compared to pay secrecy. This may be the reason for the finding of the present study that the effect of procedural justice is weaker in the prediction of pay level and pay raise. However, the paper by Colella et al. (2007) is not based on empirical findings and the literature does not provide any similar or closer empirical findings to make comparisons with the findings of the present study. Therefore, this is another contribution of the present study, which will open an area for future research.

Third, the results showed that the years of experience in public sector is an important characteristic in the determination of pay satisfaction. This suggests that public sector employees' preference for tenure-related pay mechanisms, which could encourage them to stay in public sector longer. On the one hand, apart from the monetary value of pay, longer tenure indicates an individual's importance for an organization. The findings suggest that pay level, raise and benefits protect this feature in the Sri Lankan public sector. On the other hand, this finding suggests that the number of job changes is not valued by the public sector, and stayers

have higher pay satisfaction than leavers. The findings of the present study suggest that the Sri Lankan public sector pay system “pays to stay”. Still, the findings should be interpreted with caution. On the one hand, as argued above, in an open pay system, pay level and pay raises could be narrower and, based on the arguments of Colella et al. (2007), this situation encourages employees to find better prospects elsewhere. On the other hand, the finding related to the years of work experience in the public sector suggests that stayers are rewarded than leavers. Overall, more research is needed to enhance the understanding in these areas since it is very rare to find empirical research on open systems and/or public sector.

In addition to above specific theoretical contributions to the public sector pay systems, the research study makes several other theoretical contributions and these can be discussed under six areas. First, the results of factor analysis showed that pay satisfaction comprised of four distinctive dimensions - satisfaction with pay level, raise, benefits and structure/administration. This supports Heneman and Schwab’s (1985) argument that pay level, raise, benefits and structure/administration are distinct albeit related judgments of pay satisfaction, and Williams et al.’s (2006) argument that any investigation on pay satisfaction should include all four dimensions for better prediction. Overall, results showed the suitability of Heneman and Schwab’s (1985) pay satisfaction scale for the current study context.

Second, the majority of the existing studies tested the effect of pay equity in comparison to pay referents (internal and external). Although literature suggests the importance (Rice et al., 1990), only few empirical studies (such as Kim and Garman, 2004) tested the effect of pay equity in terms of pay an employee feels he/she should receive and the pay that one needs/deserves. The present study investigated both these forms of equity as adequacy and comparative and tested the effect of these on pay satisfaction. The results of the present study showed that equity (adequacy and comparative) significantly positively predicts all the dimensions of pay satisfaction. Therefore, this is one of the novel contributions of the study.

Third, the effect of justice on pay satisfaction of public sector employees is rarely empirically tested. Therefore, against this backdrop, the present study makes an important contribution for the literature on justice, pay satisfaction and public sector. As presented in the section on results, the relative contribution of the three dimensions of justice on four dimensions

of pay satisfaction varied. This has implications for practice, which are discussed in the next section.

Fourth, the present study investigated the effect of love of money on pay satisfaction. Specifically, the presented study was interested in the success dimension of love of money on pay satisfaction, and as stated by Tang (1995) success emerged as a distinctive dimension of love of money in the present study. When love of money is considered to represent an employee's attitudes toward money, it can be used as his/her frame of reference in judging pay satisfaction. The results showed that love of money significantly negatively predicts all four dimensions of pay satisfaction. As discussed in the next section, this finding has important implications for organizations' pay practices.

Fifth, the literature emphasizes the importance of individual and socio-demographic characteristics in the prediction of individuals' attitudes. Instead of controlling or neglecting the effects of individual and socio-demographic characteristics, the present study tested direct effects of seven such characteristics. The results showed that three of these characteristics, namely, work experience, income earners and dependents have significant effect on pay satisfaction. In this regard, it is very rare to find empirical studies that tested the effect of these variables on pay satisfaction (see Murphy et al., 2020). Therefore, the present study makes an important contribution for the literature on pay satisfaction and public sector.

Sixth, the present study evaluated gender differences on the perceptions of equity, love of money and justice. This analysis can be considered as a by-product of the analysis. The results showed the significance of gender on the prediction of love of money, where females have a stronger perception of love of money than males. Since the present study evaluated the success dimension of love of money, the results specifically suggest that females have more positive attitudes towards the success dimension of love of money. On the one hand, Prince (1993) argues that even though both men and women consider money as a symbol and vehicle of success, it is more of a direct and undisguised source for men compared to women. On the other hand, the literature on changing gendered norms in society and dual-earner families (such as Atkinson and Boles, 1984) suggests that men reporting pride in career success of their wives. In Sri Lanka, an important observation is the increasing number of educated women entering

into the economically active population. These data suggest the importance of further investigating effects of gender on employment related aspects (see Feng et al., 2020).

Implications for practice

When considering specific implications for public sector pay practices, open pay systems make information related to individual pay levels and raises accessible. Employees are able to make numerous pay comparisons on their inputs and outcome (pay). However, employees are not in a position or unable to obtain the information on referent others of their inputs. An employee may be aware about his/her inputs, in terms of such as performance evaluation and/or pay for performance data. However, not knowing of other employees' (referents') pay provides incomplete picture and could lead to unfair perceptions. This situation may threaten the sustainability of even better designed, developed and administered pay systems.

Further, for employees to develop high levels of perceptions on equity and justice, adequate information should be provided in a clear and concise manner, and those should be made available to employees by easy access. In this regard, on the one hand, the provision of government circulars or directives addressing pay systems such as how pay revisions are made and how pay related policies or procedures changed should be supplied in a simple to digest manner to employees. On the other hand, the public sector with compared to the private sector are slower in adopting information and communication technologies (ICT), and this slowness is highly evident in the context of developing countries.

Furthermore, pay-related individual information, such as how performance is appraised, how pay raise is influenced by pay for performance policies and how group-based pay is determined, need to be clearly explained to employees to generate more positive perception on pay satisfaction. In this regard, the role of supervisors is important. Therefore, more attention should be given to interpersonal and communication skills of supervisors, and necessary actions should be taken to improve their skills.

In addition, the study provides several other implications for practices, namely, first, pay satisfaction has both positive and negative consequences, such as productivity gains and absenteeism. Hence, the pay satisfaction of employees is a topic of importance to pay advocates

and administrators across the world. The results of factor analysis showed that pay structure/administration and benefits are the most important dimensions of pay satisfaction over pay level and pay raise. This suggests that simply increasing pay levels and raises by throwing money would not improve employees pay satisfaction. Therefore, the dimensions of pay have to be managed effectively for the advantage of employees and employers. Specific implications for public sector are dealt with separately in the next section.

Second, the present study evaluated several antecedents to pay satisfaction. When considering equity as a predictor of pay satisfaction, its effect (both adequacy and comparative) is strongest on pay level. The economic theories of job competition models assert that minimum pay levels of jobs are established/decided in labour markets, where potential employees compete for jobs, not for pay. The pay level of public sector jobs may not be as high as the private sector due to the competition in the labour market; the public sector may not be attracted to the best in the country since pay levels are comparatively low. In the circumstances, individual level equity based on pay employees feel they deserve could also be low. In this regard, equity termed adequacy emerged as a significant predictor of pay satisfaction, which includes pay referents in terms of economic needs, desires and self-validations. However, only few previous studies (such as Kim and Garman, 2004) emphasized the importance of incorporating these in pay equity, suggesting this pay referent is less common in designing pay systems. With regard to comparative, as a developing country, Sri Lankan public sector may not have financial strength to match pay levels to market rates to maintain external equity or may not conduct periodic job analysis or job evaluations to achieve internal equity. This may create limitations in maintaining equity in terms of internal-between jobs, internal-within jobs, and external-same job. However, the results suggest that the perception of equity is vital for pay satisfaction. Therefore, organizations should pay more attention to job evaluation for internal-between job comparisons, pay adjustment procedures for internal-within job comparisons, and labour market salary surveys for external-same job comparisons to enhance the employees' perception of equity. On the other hand, employees and their representatives (such as trade unions) need to be communicated that pay systems are implicitly and obviously based on contribution, and it is the easiest and the most appropriate justification for any pay differentials.

Third, love of money predicts pay satisfaction significantly and negatively; the effect is strongest for satisfaction with pay level. The literature on money suggests that if employees are satisfied with their money (pay), they may not be obsessed with it. Tang (1995, p. 815) state “those who value money do not necessarily have a higher income than those who do not; those who value money tend to have a high level of pay dissatisfaction”. Further, employees use pay as the ‘frame of reference’ when making judgements on pay satisfaction. On the one hand, although organizations do not have direct control over employees’ love of money, organizations should be in control to manage employees’ pay- not only pay levels but also raises and benefits. On the other hand, Gentina et al. (2020) found that mindfulness reduces the love of money (avaricious monetary aspiration, or greed), which suggest the importance of enhancing mindfulness in people. Therefore, the findings of the present study have important implications for organizations pay practices.

Fourth, the present study is one of the few empirical studies in recent times that investigated the effect of all three forms of justice on pay satisfaction. When organizations are aware of the relative strength of each dimension of justice on each dimension of pay satisfaction, design, implementation and administration of pay systems would be more effective. For example, it was found that the effect of distributive justice is strongest on pay level followed by pay raise. Distributive justice is based on the evaluations of person-referenced outcomes, and organizations should concentrate more on performance appraisal and merit pay systems. Procedural justice is based on the evaluations of organizational systems, and organizations should concentrate on policies and procedures of rewards allocation. Interactional justice is based on agent-referenced outcomes, and organizations should concentrate on supervisors’ role and feedback mechanisms of pay systems. The present study provided valuable information on the relative importance of these in determining each dimension of pay satisfaction. Distributive justice is stronger for pay level and raise; procedural justice is stronger for pay structure/administration and benefits; interactional justice is stronger for all four dimensions of pay satisfaction. The findings suggest that the assumptions of distributive and procedural justice perceptions on pay satisfaction do not vary even for public sector and for a developing country context. With regard to interactional justice, the current understanding has limits due to the

rarity of studies on the effect of interactional justice (as combined or separately as interpersonal and informational) on pay satisfaction. The present study revealed that interactional justice has positive significant effect on all four dimensions of pay satisfaction. Therefore, organizations have to invest on creating fair decision-making processes and communication and feedback mechanisms to encourage employee voice, reduce errors in organizational decisions, and communicate information about organizational systems such as rewards, performance management, job analysis and job evaluation. Organizations have to manage the perception of justice for employees to have a feeling of pay satisfaction. In most situations the provision of such information is considered to lay with managers/supervisors.

Conclusion

The research investigated the determinants of pay satisfaction of executive-level employees in public sector in Sri Lanka. It was found equity, love of money and justice strongly predict pay satisfaction. It was found that the contribution of each dimension, for example justice, on each dimension of pay satisfaction is different. The years of work experience in public sector, the number of income earners in the family and the number of dependents in the family were identified as individual and socio-demographic characteristics that contribute for pay satisfaction. A detailed discussion of these was made in the sections of results and discussion of results. Overall, of the total of 10 variables tested in the study, six emerged as significant predictors of pay satisfaction. Therefore, it is evident that employees prefer to use multiple criteria in making judgements about their pay satisfaction. Since satisfaction with pay has important consequences for any organization, understanding the antecedents is important and has important implications. The implications of the findings for both theory and practice, with some implications specific to public sector, open pay systems and developing countries, were also discussed in detail in the above sections.

Limitations

First, due to the rarity of studies on public sector, open pay systems and developing country contexts, the present study relied on traditional well-established predictors of pay satisfaction,

namely equity, love of money, justice, and individual and socio-demographic predictors. Having said that, although interactional justice is well-established in justice literature, it is not widely tested as a predictor of pay satisfaction. This situation also applies to work experience, the number of income earners and the number of dependents. Second, determinants to be incorporated in an empirical study solely depend on the prevalence of such in the research context; when lump-sum bonuses and team pay for performance plans for example are not in operation, these cannot be studied. Third, as stated by Kumar et al. (2017), pay satisfaction could be viewed from other angles such as from the angle of 'convenience' (payment modalities, multiple methods to pay, transactions), which is a necessity and developing in public sector (e.g. Healthcare). Fourth, the investigation on love of money was confined to success dimension even though Tang (1995) proposed several money attitudes of individuals such as importance, risk and evil. Fifth, the present study analysed direct effects. We used SPSS for the analysis. If sample is larger and fairly distributed among subgroups, for example by marital status, mediations and moderations could have been studied, i.e., whether marital status moderates pay satisfaction. Further, other statistical software like AMOS could have been used for the analysis of moderators and mediators. In addition, two-way ANOVA could have been used to obtain better explanations, such as how age and gender together explain pay satisfaction. Finally, the present study identified that the number of dependents in the family is a significant predictor of pay satisfaction. In an Asian culture, and also in a developing country context where care systems are not developed, dependents living in a family could be of various types. In addition to dependent children, elders can also be included as dependents, and the present study had not make a difference between who these dependents were.

Areas for future research

Based on the insights of the present study, future research can be designed as in depth investigations. First, future studies could broaden determinants by incorporating variables such as team incentive plans. Second, as mentioned earlier, several combinations of moderator and mediator relationships could be investigated. Third, future research could incorporate other money attitudes of love of money to enhance the understanding. In doing so, data could be

analysed using structural equation modelling techniques. Fourth, if the public sector is identified as the most ethical employer compared to all other sectors, such as private, small businesses and family businesses, the way in which public sector practices could be transferred to other sectors to create a country-wide ethical business climate is an interesting area of research, especially, in developing countries' context. Finally, the present study evaluated gender differences in perceptions of equity, love of money and justice, and showed significant gender differences in the prediction of love of money. Based on the insights of the present study, future research can be designed as in-depth investigations.

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Tables

Table 1. Factor analysis – equity

	F1: Adequacy	F2: Comparative
Pay is sufficient to cover my social commitments	.855	
Pay is sufficient to save some money for my future	.823	
Pay is sufficient to cover my incidental expenses	.818	
Pay is sufficient to cover my living expenses	.754	
Pay is fair with compared to others at other comparable public sector organizations		.781
Pay is fair with compared to others in my organization		.763
Pay is fair with compared to other colleagues at the labour market		.726
Eigenvalue	4.19	2.28
% of variance	43.47	19.86
Cronbach's alpha	.862	.762
AVE	.66	.57
Construct reliability	.89	.80

Table 2. Factor analysis – love of money

	F1. Love of money
Money can give me the opportunity to be what I want to be	.887
Money represents my achievements	.859
Money is a symbol of my success	.818
Money makes people respect me in the community	.797
Money is important	.763
Money helps me to express my competence and abilities	.746
I value money very highly	.739
Money gives me autonomy and freedom	.730
Eigenvalue	4.31
% of variance	60.13
Cronbach's alpha	.862
AVE	.61
Construct reliability	.93

Table 3. Factor analysis – justice

	F1: Interactional justice	F2: Distributive justice	F3: Procedural justice
When decisions are made about my job, my immediate superior takes steps to deal with me in a truthful manner	.924		
When decisions are made about my job, my immediate superior shows concern for my rights as an employee	.880		
When decisions are made about my job, my immediate superior treats me with kindness and consideration	.876		
When decisions are made about my job, my immediate superior considers my view point	.822		
When decisions are made about my job, my immediate superior provides me with timely feedback about his/her decisions and their implications	.801		
When decisions are made about my job, my immediate superior is able to suppress personal biases	.750		
My organization rewards me in view of the amount of effort I put forth		.884	
My organization rewards me in view of the work I have done well		.880	
My organization rewards me in view of the stresses and strains of my job		.833	
My organization rewards me in view of the amount of experience I have		.829	
My organization rewards me in view of our responsibilities		.827	
There are procedures designed to allow for requests for clarification or additional information about the decisions			.889
There are procedures designed to provide useful feedback regarding the decisions and their implementation			.880
There are procedures designed to generate standards so that decisions could be made with consistency			.872
There are procedures designed to provide opportunities to appeal or challenge the decisions			.811
There are procedures designed to collect accurate information necessary for making decisions			.858
Eigenvalue	4.22	3.05	2.44
% of variance	32.46	23.47	18.74
Cronbach's alpha	.912	.897	.880
AVE	.71	.72	.74
Construct reliability	.93	.92	.94

Table 4. Factor analysis – pay satisfaction

	F1: Structure/ Administration	F2: Benefits	F2: Level	F3: Raise
Satisfaction with consistency of pay policies	.826			
Satisfaction with pay of other jobs in the organization	.769			
Satisfaction with my pay structure	.767			
Satisfaction with information given about pay	.736			
Satisfaction with differences in pay among jobs in the organization	.734			
Satisfaction with how pay is administered	.725			
The value of my benefits		.784		
My benefit package		.752		
The number of benefits I receive		.738		
The amount paid towards my benefits		.710		
Satisfaction with how my raises are determined			.844	
Satisfaction with influence my supervisor has on my pay			.836	
Satisfaction with my most recent raise			.791	
Satisfaction with the raises I have typically received in the past			.717	
Satisfaction with my current salary				.889
Satisfaction with my take-home pay				.887
Satisfaction with size of my current salary				.798
Satisfaction with my overall level of pay				.758
Eigenvalue	4.654	3.907	2.820	1.546
% of variance	26.54	22.37	18.07	8.48
Cronbach's alpha	.781	.739	.829	.857
AVE	.58	.56	.64	.70
Construct reliability	.87	.83	.88	.90

Table 5. Correlation

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	
1 Age [†]	-	-	-																	
2 Sex [†]	-	-	-.116	-																
3 Marital status [†]	-	-	.410**	-.035	-															
4 Dependents	2.03	1.07	.176*	.112	.140*	-														
5 Income earners	2.09	1.49	.143*	.082	.145*	.104	-													
6 Education [†]	-	-	.316**	.103	.066	.128	.044	-												
7 Ex in Pub	13.50	9.71	.417**	.131	.059	.088	.032	.131	-											
8 E-Adequacy	3.29	.87	.115	.124	.163*	.165*	.169**	.142*	.096	.81										
9 E-Comparative	3.52	.77	.128	.106	.113	.152*	.113	.124	.130	.155*	.75									
10 Love of money	3.92	.73	-.149*	.313**	.170*	.148*	.146*	.141*	.116	-.131*	.109	.78								
11 D-justice	4.11	.91	.121	.082	.129	.201*	.138	.128	.164*	.160*	.174*	.093	.85							
12 P-justice	3.82	.81	.111	.117	.137	.208*	.065	.116	.153*	.183*	.152*	.111	.399**	.86						
13 I-justice	4.47	.76	.118	.161	.109	.118	.071	.092	.168*	.129	.098	.137	.339**	.369**	.84					
14 S-Level	3.54	.97	.129	.128	.054	-.207*	.203*	.101	.233*	.416**	.388**	-.316**	.384**	.396**	.322**	.84				
15 S-Raise	3.37	.84	.099	.125	.068	-.219*	.222*	.093	.217*	.385**	.308**	-.330**	.375**	.325**	.340**	.391**	.80			
16 S-Benefits	3.69	.74	.104	.122	.085	-.221*	.234*	.115	.272*	.336**	.365**	-.359**	.374**	.312**	.284**	.363**	.397**	.75		
17 S-Structure	3.78	.69	.095	.108	.093	-.099	.124	.103	.237*	.364**	.384**	-.333**	.362**	.322**	.332**	.354**	.388**	.357**	.76	

Note: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001; diagonal entries, square root of AVE where appropriate; off-diagonal entries, correlation between constructs; † Constructs are on dichotomous scales. Ex in Pub = years of experience in public sector.

Table 6. Regression Results

Step	Variable	P-Level			P-Raise			P-Benefits			P-Structure						
		β	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics	β	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics	β	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics	β	R ² (Adj.)	Change statistics				
1	Experience in public sector	.126*	.099*	.062	3.306*	.100*	.077	.051	2.123*	.112*	.059	.047	1.649	.144*	.011	.023	1.914
	Income earners	.103*				.087				.102*				.033			
	Dependents	-.136*				-.111*				-.091				-.037			
2	Experience in public sector	.123*	.775***	.752	61.437***	.104*	.559***	.527	32.383***	.114*	.641***	.633	51.731***	.146*	.621***	.614	32.649***
	Income earners	.108*				.101*				.110*				.048			
	Dependents	-.124*				-.113*				-.108*				-.066			
	E-Adequacy	.602***				.279**				.456***				.411***			
	E-Comparative	.524***				.216**				.331***				.389***			
	Love of money	-.435***				-.368***				-.394***				-.346***			
	D-justice	.501***				.490***				.382***				.402***			
	P-justice	.327***				.339***				.358***				.370***			
	I-justice	.355***				.343***				.214**				.361***			

Note: * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001

Table 7. Summary – Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis	Result	Description
H1 (equity)	Supported	Both components significantly positively predicted all components of pay satisfaction; the effect of both adequacy and comparative are highest on pay level.
H2 (love of money)	Supported	Significantly negatively predicted all components of pay satisfaction; the effect of love of money is highest on satisfaction with pay level.
H3a (justice- distributive)	Supported	Significantly positively predicted all components of pay satisfaction; the effects of distributive justice on satisfaction with pay level and raise are the highest.
H3b (justice- procedural)	supported	Significantly positively predicted all components of pay satisfaction; the effects of procedural justice on satisfaction with pay structure/ is the highest followed by benefits.
H3c (justice- interactional)	Supported	Significantly positively predicted all components of pay satisfaction; the effects of interactional justice on satisfaction with benefits is the lowest.
H4 (gender)	Not supported	Did not show significant effect on any component of pay satisfaction.
H5 (highest level of education)	Not supported	Did not show significant effect on any component of pay satisfaction.
H6 (age)	Not supported	Did not show significant effect on any component of pay satisfaction.
H7 (years of work experience in public sector)	Supported	Employees with more years of work experience in the public sector were more satisfied with their pay.
H8 (marital status)	Not supported	Did not show significant effect on any component of pay satisfaction.
H9 (number of income earners in the family)	Partially supported	Significantly positively predicted pay level, pay raise, and benefits. The effect on pay structure/administration is positive but not statistically significant.
H10 (number of dependents in the family)	Partially supported	Significantly negatively predicted pay level, pay raise and benefits. The effect on pay structure/administration is negative but not statistically significant

Table 8. Gender differences in equity, love of money and justice

	Male		Female		<i>t</i>
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
E-Adequacy	3.27	.79	3.32	.93	-520
E-Comparative	3.44	.77	3.61	.75	-1.768
Love of money	4.36	.80	4.60	.68	-2.692**
D-justice	4.08	.86	4.13	.93	-.530
P-justice	3.82	.79	3.94	.80	-.289
I-justice	3.90	.77	3.94	.68	-.547

Note: ** p < 0.01

Appendix 1. Selected demographic characteristics of employees in public sector of Sri Lanka

	Gender		Age		Highest level of education			Marital status		
	Male	Female	20-39 yrs	40-60 yrs	Less than Bachelor's	Bachelor's only	Postgraduate	Married	Single	
Total in public sector	865,669 (=100%)	51%	49%	47%	53%	71%	20%	9%	84%	16%
Highest level of education:										
Total with Bachelor's degree only	170,103 (=100%)	33%	67%	N/A						
Total with postgraduate degree	79,327 (=100%)	38%	62%							
Total at or above Bachelor's degree	249,430 (=100%)	35%	65%							
Total married	726,861 (=100%)	51%	49%							

Note: Single includes all other categories, i.e., never married, separated, divorced, widowed and not specified.

Appendix 1 was developed by the Author; data were extracted from pages 56, 84, 92, 93 and 97 of Department of Census and Statistics (2018); N/A = data not specified by the Source.

Figure

Figure 1. Conceptual model